

BISTABILITY OF COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

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SUMMARY

Multistability of composite thin structures has shown potential for morphing applications. The present work focuses on bistability of composite cylindrical shells. It aims to gather the analytical understanding to design bistability in to shells and to define and study the parameters constraining their design envelope.

Keywords: Bistability, Morphing, Anisotropy, Continuation.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, interest in morphing structures has increased due to the superior benefits that they can provide. A structure that is able to change its shape and “tune itself” to meet different operational requirements is attractive. With respect to aerospace structures, shape control of aerodynamic components can potentially offer significant improvements in performance.

One of the current aims is to gather the understanding to design materials and obtain tailored structural responses by exploiting the capabilities that anisotropy gives. This project seeks to establish capabilities for analytical modelling and optimum design of novel composite structures that achieve shape change by actuation from one stable state to another i.e. bistability.

Bistability may be designed in to laminates such that the application of a threshold value of load or piezoelectric strain, for example, can achieve a controlled jump from one shape to another. The key feature for morphing applications is that, once in the alternative stable state, no energy/power is needed to maintain this shape.

Current work relates to the development of an analytical model and to the definition and study of the parameters constraining the design envelope of multistable composite structures. The feasibility of potential applications will depend on the “shape” of this design envelope. Dedicated literature shows that both anisotropy and laminates' shape may have an important role.

THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT AND NUMERICAL SOLUTION

Cured flat, unsymmetric epoxy-matrix composite laminates will develop curvature when cooled to room temperature. The curvatures are due to a mismatch in the thermal expansion behaviour of the layers within the laminate. Hyer investigated the shapes of

several families of unsymmetric laminates and observed that the room-temperature shapes do not always conform to the prediction of classical lamination theory [1]. Instead of being a saddle shape, as predicted by the classical theory, many unsymmetric laminates have a cylindrical shape at room temperature. In addition, a second cylindrical shape can sometimes be obtained by a simple snap-through action. Hyer incorporated geometric nonlinearities into the classical theory to explain this behaviour. To correctly predict the room temperature shapes of cross-ply laminates, Hyer and Hamamoto developed a nonlinear approach based on polynomial approximations of the displacements and used a Rayleigh-Ritz minimisation of total potential energy [2]. Following the aforementioned works many researcher undertook studies aiming at either deepening the physical insight and the modelling abilities or finding morphing related applications [3-8].

An approach similar to Hyer's will be used here to investigate bistability of unsymmetrically laminated cylindrical shells. It will involve the use of the novel shell model developed by the authors [9] which include Qatu's recommendations on the effects of initial curvature on shells' anisotropy [10].

Equilibrium configurations are solutions to a set of nonlinear algebraic equations deriving from the Rayleigh-Ritz minimisation. The resulting set of equations depends upon physical parameters such as the room temperature. In the current approach, we continue numerical solutions in parameter space, that is, we path-follow equilibrium configurations as the control parameter varies, find stable and unstable configurations and detect bifurcations. The numerics is carried out using EPCont [11], a set of Matlab routines for numerical continuation. Results will be validated against finite elements analysis.

Problem Definition

The aim of this work is to investigate bistability of cylindrical composite panels with particular attention given to the description of the solution procedure. In fact, it is noted that this study is intended as a benchmark for the general solution technique. This procedure has been developed to be generally applicable to a whole set of bistability related problems in such a way as to allow a more general investigation on the design space of morphing bistable laminated structures.

The system that will be analysed is essentially a cylindrical panel moulded with radius of curvature R and a square inplane shape of side L . The panel is an unsymmetric laminate with stacking sequence $[0_2 90_2]$. The structure has free edges, is clamped in its central point and is subject to the thermal load due to the cool-down from cure to room temperature.

Finite element analyses show that this structure has two stable shapes at room temperature. These shapes will be found by using the Ritz method that is minimising a polynomial expansion of the total potential energy.

Total Potential Energy and Shell Model

Previous work [1-8, 12, 13] has shown that some factors may have a crucial role affecting the bistability of laminated composite structures and consequentially, the

design of morphing structures. Some of these factors are: anisotropy, laminates' shape and geometrically nonlinear deformations. For these reasons, use is made of the shell model developed by the authors [9]. It considers shells of general shape so, for current purposes is specialised to cylinders. It is assumed that the middle surface of the shell structure is described by the curvilinear coordinate system (ξ_1, ξ_2, ζ) , where ξ_1 and ξ_2 are coordinates, longitudinal and radial respectively, describing the position on the middle surface and ζ is the coordinate in the thickness direction. This being the case, the principal radii of curvature are respectively $R_1 = \infty$ and $R_2 = R$ and, by assuming von Karman nonlinearities and surface displacements to be

$$\begin{aligned} u(\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta) &= u_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) + \zeta \phi_1(\xi_1, \xi_2) \\ v(\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta) &= v_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) + \zeta \phi_2(\xi_1, \xi_2) \\ w(\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta) &= w_0(\xi_1, \xi_2), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

the nonlinear strains are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_4 \\ \varepsilon_5 \\ \varepsilon_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} e_1^0 + \zeta e_1^1 + \frac{1}{8}(e_5^0 - \kappa_2^0)^2 \\ \frac{e_2^0 + \zeta e_2^1}{1 + \zeta/R} + \frac{1}{8} \frac{(e_4^0 + \kappa_1^0)^2}{(1 + \zeta/R)^2} \\ \frac{e_4^0}{1 + \zeta/R} \\ e_5^0 \\ \omega_1^0 + \zeta \omega_1^1 + \frac{\omega_2^0 + \zeta \omega_2^1}{1 + \zeta/R} + \frac{1}{4} \frac{(e_5^0 - \kappa_2^0)(e_4^0 + \kappa_1^0)}{(1 + \zeta/R)} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} e_1^0 &= \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial \xi_1} & e_2^0 &= \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{\partial v_0}{\partial \xi_2} + w_0 \right) \\ \omega_1^0 &= \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial \xi_1} & \omega_2^0 &= \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial \xi_2} \\ e_4^0 &= \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial \xi_2} + R \phi_2 - v_0 \right) & e_5^0 &= \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial \xi_1} + \phi_1 \\ \kappa_1^0 &= \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial \xi_2} - v_0 - R \phi_2 \right) & \kappa_2^0 &= -\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial \xi_1} + \phi_1 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$e_1^1 = \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial \xi_1} \quad e_2^1 = \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial \xi_2}$$

$$\omega_1^1 = \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial \xi_1} \quad \omega_2^1 = \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial \xi_2}.$$

The total potential energy can then be written as [14]

$$\Pi = \int_{\Omega} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \bar{\mathbf{Q}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\chi}^T \bar{\mathbf{Q}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \Delta T \right) \cdot R \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{R} \right) d\zeta d\xi_1 d\xi_2 \quad (4)$$

where Ω denotes the midsurface, h the thickness, and $\bar{\mathbf{Q}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\chi}$ are the transformed stiffness matrix and the transformed thermal coefficient vector, respectively.

Polynomial Approximation

The displacements are assumed to be

$$u_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \sum_{m=0}^N \sum_{n=0}^m U_{n,m-n} \xi_1^n \xi_2^{n-m}$$

$$v_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \sum_{m=0}^N \sum_{n=0}^m V_{n,m-n} \xi_1^n \xi_2^{n-m}$$

$$w_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \sum_{m=0}^N \sum_{n=0}^m W_{n,m-n} \xi_1^n \xi_2^{n-m} \quad (5)$$

$$\phi_1(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \sum_{m=0}^N \sum_{n=0}^m X_{n,m-n} \xi_1^n \xi_2^{n-m}$$

$$\phi_2(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \sum_{m=0}^N \sum_{n=0}^m Y_{n,m-n} \xi_1^n \xi_2^{n-m}$$

In other words, displacements are approximated by a complete polynomial basis truncated to order N . The coefficients $U_{n,m-n}$, $V_{n,m-n}$, $W_{n,m-n}$, $X_{n,m-n}$, $Y_{n,m-n}$ are unknowns and, together with Equation (1) they uniquely define the displacements u , v , w . For the sake of simplicity, the same polynomial order is used for all the displacement components for a total of $5(N+1)(N+2)/2$ unknowns. Nevertheless, by respecting the essential boundary conditions and imposing symmetries, this number can be reduced. In particular, the following conditions are enforced:

- u_0 and ϕ_1 are odd functions in ξ_1 and even functions in ξ_2

- v_0 and ϕ_2 are even functions in ξ_1 and odd functions in ξ_2
- w_0 is even in ξ_1 and ξ_2 , and it vanishes at the origin

Plugging the resulting polynomial decomposition in Equation (4) and collecting all the unknown coefficients in a vector \mathbf{c} , the total potential energy is approximated by

$$\Pi \approx \Pi_N(\mathbf{c}, \Delta T) \quad (6)$$

which is now an algebraic function of the Lagrangian variables and temperature.

Solution Technique and Parameter Continuation

For fixed ΔT , an equilibrium is a local minimum of the function Π_N . It is found by solving the system of nonlinear algebraic equations

$$f_i(\mathbf{c}, \Delta T) = \frac{\partial \Pi_N}{\partial c_i} = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{c}, \Delta T) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (7)$$

As stated in the previous sections, the current aim is to explore the design space in a systematic fashion. In order to do so, we use a numerical continuation approach. Starting from $(\mathbf{c}_0, 0)$, the equilibrium solution for $\Delta T = 0$, it is possible to trace the locus of equilibria at different temperatures. This is done via a suitable parametrisation $(\mathbf{c}(s), \Delta T(s))$ passing by $(\mathbf{c}_0, 0)$ and satisfying

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{c}(s), \Delta T(s)) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (8)$$

The locus $(\mathbf{c}(s), \Delta T(s))$ is called a solution branch. An advantage of numerical continuation is that it computes stable as well as unstable solutions, as far as they belong to the same solution branch. For instance, let us consider the bifurcation diagram presented by Hyer in [2]. For ΔT close to zero, the only solution is a saddle. At a critical temperature, the saddle becomes unstable and two other stable cylindrical solutions appear. A numerical simulation in which ΔT was varied quasi-statically would fail to compute the unstable saddle, whereas in the numerical continuation approach, stable and unstable saddles are computed naturally, as they belong to the same solution branch $(\mathbf{c}(s), \Delta T(s))$. Another immediate application, in which such features would be useful, is in tracing the nonlinear force-displacement diagram (complete with hysteresis) for a panel subject to snap-through.

In the present work, the expression for \mathbf{f} is computed symbolically via Maple 11. The resulting system of equation is exported as Matlab code and continued with EPCont. The results presented here concern only continuations in the parameter ΔT , but the

proposed approach can be extended to any other design parameter, such as the radius of curvature or the side length.

RESULTS

In this section we present numerical results obtained by continuing the system of Equations (7), when $N = 5$, $L = 0.25 \text{ m}$ and $R = 0.5 \text{ m}$. This polynomial order is a good compromise between accuracy and computational efficiency and it matches finite element analysis adequately.

In Figure 1 we can see the continuation diagram for a cylindrical panel. Namely we plot $W_{2,0}$ and $W_{0,2}$ against the continuation parameter ΔT . Amongst all Lagrangian coordinates, we chose $W_{2,0}$ and $W_{0,2}$ as they are representative of the curvature at the origin. As expected, the continuation diagram features two branches. The same diagram, on the other hand, shows the presence of three equilibria, one of which is unstable, at room temperature.

Figure 1 – Bifurcation diagram (ΔT in $^{\circ}\text{C}$, $W_{2,0}$ in m^{-1} , $W_{0,2}$ in m). Blue and red colours refer to continuation from/to equilibria 1 and 3. Unstable branches are represented by dashed lines.

The room temperature equilibrium labelled 1 in Figure 1 is approximately a cylinder oriented as the moulded structure, but with greater curvature. Its shape is shown in Figure 2. For this solution, $W_{0,2}$ is large, compared to $W_{2,0}$. Conversely, the equilibrium labelled 3, and shown in Figure 3, is a cylinder whose principle curvature is normal to that of the moulded panel ($W_{2,0}$ is large, compared to $W_{0,2}$). Following solution 3 in parameter space along the red branch, we found that around $\Delta T = -40 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ the solutions get unstable via a saddle-node bifurcation. At $\Delta T = -180 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ we obtain a connected unstable equilibrium, labelled 2, for which $W_{0,2}$ and $W_{2,0}$ are comparable. Notably, the stable solutions 1 and 3 are disconnected in parameter space.

The physical interpretation of this scenario is depicted in Figure 4. Starting from the cure temperature (labelled 0), the system follows the blue branch until equilibrium 1.

The reverse path is also possible. On the other hand, it is possible to start from equilibrium 3 on the red branch and heat up the structure: after an initial deformation, the system will jump to the blue branch and will eventually reach point 0. Conversely, we will never reach 3 by simply cooling down from 0. In fact, an external intervention (i.e. an applied force) is necessary to make the structure snap on the red branch and follow the equilibrium 3 branch.

Figure 2 – Equilibrium 1, Finite Element Analysis (light blue surface) against analytical results (blue grid). Mould shape (Equilibrium 0) in grey.

Figure 3 – Equilibrium 3, FEA (light red surface) against analytical results (red grid). Mould shape (Equilibrium 0) in grey.

Such a feature is particularly interesting as it is peculiar to initially curved panels. A similar behaviour has been shown by Hyer in [2]. Initially flat plates behave according to the classical pitchfork scenario: equilibria analogous to 1 and 3 can be followed from point 0 and vice versa; imperfect plates on the other hand behave accordingly to Figure 4.

We have benchmarked our code against finite elements simulations, performed with the commercial software ABAQUS. The panel is modelled using 1764 four-node-square

shell elements (S4R) with a total of 1849 nodes. Mesh refinement studies showed that the chosen mesh density, given acceptable computational time, gave sufficiently accurate results; indeed further refinement gave a negligible change in results. The cool-down and snap-through processes are simulated by using ‘*Static, General*’ steps with ‘*Nlgeom*’ on. When convergence was difficult to achieve use has been made of the option ‘*stabilization with: dissipated energy fraction*’. This option makes the simulation pseudo-dynamic by adding fictitious viscous forces to damp instabilities and improves the convergence properties of the system. This allows the structure to jump to the different branches of the solution as indicated by the black line in Figure 4.

A comparison between the stable shapes obtained with both methods is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, and it shows an excellent agreement. The approach proposed here matches finite element analysis precision with a substantially smaller amount of unknowns. This is largely due to the fact that the polynomial expansions (5) are already a good guess of the possible solutions.

Figure 4 – Bifurcation diagram and natural evolution of the system subject to temperature variations (black line). ΔT in $^{\circ}\text{C}$, $W_{2,0}$ in m^{-1} .

In Figures 5 to 8 we analyse in better details the convergence of our method against finite elements. Let \mathbf{u} be the displacements obtained in Cartesian coordinates with the continuation methods, and let \mathbf{u}_{FE} be the corresponding finite elements displacements. Then we can define the scalar error e as

$$e(x, y) = \|\mathbf{u}(x, y) - \mathbf{u}_{FE}(x, y)\| \quad (9)$$

Figures 5 and 7 show the cross-section errors $e(0, y)$ and $e(x, 0)$ for equilibria 1 and 3 respectively. Figures 6 and 8 show $e(x, y)$ for the full panel. The achieved tolerance is always below 10^{-3} , which is accurate in view of the degrees of freedom employed in the calculation.

Figure 5 – Equilibrium 1: Norm of the difference between finite elements analysis and model results along the middle sections ($x = 0$ solid line, $y = 0$ dash dotted line, dimensions in m).

Figure 6 – Equilibrium 1: Norm of the difference between finite elements analysis and model results. The colour bar refers to the error $e(x,y)$. Dimensions in m .

Figure 7 – Equilibrium 3: Norm of the difference between finite elements analysis and model results along the middle sections ($x = 0$ solid line, $y = 0$ dash dotted line, dimensions in m).

Figure 8 – Equilibrium 1: Norm of the difference between finite elements analysis and model results. The colour bar refers to the error $e(x,y)$. Dimensions in m .

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have developed a methodology for a systematic investigation of bistability-related problems. As a test case, we have studied the bistability of a cylindrical panel.

Firstly, we have adopted the shell theory proposed in [9] which takes into account features that are found to play a fundamental role in bistability problems. A comparison between the results obtained by using this theory and other classical theories is beyond the scope of this paper. However, it is noted that the adoption of this theory has led to a better agreement with finite elements results.

Secondly, we have characterised the behaviour of a cylindrical panel subject to thermal load. The system has shown peculiarities, i.e. the broken pitchfork continuation diagram, which make it different from previously studied bistable systems, such as cured flat plates.

Lastly, we have used continuation methods to explore the design space. In the present paper we have studied the behaviour of the structure subject to temperature variations. Nevertheless, this approach can be extended to other design parameters such as in-plane shape, radius of curvature of the mould or applied loads. Relevant results will be provided in future works.

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